

In the era of AI art, what is a designer's future? A Comparative Study of the Perception of AI Art among Indian Graphic Design Students and Graphic Design Professionals

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Abstract: This study explores the perceptions of AI-generated art among graphic design graduates and working professionals in India, focusing on creative adaptation, originality concerns, and transitions to new tools. Using a mixed-methods approach, qualitative and quantitative data were collected to identify key differences in how these groups use and accept AI tools. The findings reveal that professionals integrate AI to streamline workflows and enhance ideation, viewing it as a supportive tool rather than a replacement. In contrast, students express heightened anxiety about AI's impact on originality and job prospects, often shaped by media narratives. A notable observation is the "Adoption Window Awareness" among professionals, reflecting the strategic use of emerging AI tools, compared to students' reliance on older technologies.

Practical Implications: This study underscores the importance of incorporating AI education into design curricula and addressing ethical considerations in AI adoption. By examining these dynamics within a culturally diverse context, the research provides valuable insights into the evolving interplay between AI and creative practices.

Keywords: AI art; Design; Ethics. Image generators; Student Opinions.

1. Introduction

Generative image tools installed in computer systems are software solutions that enable the generation of images from text prompts or any given data using artificial intelligence. Such tools utilize several advanced deep learning techniques including GANs, and diffusion models among others to produce anything from very basic designs to very complex and realistic images. The likes of DALL-E and Midjourney have in the recent past changed the landscape of creative tasks through very fast and tailored visual content generation. Nonetheless, while these tools help in generating and customizing content efficiently and quickly, these tools also generate fears of lack of originality and perhaps replacement of traditional creative roles. Several studies have been conducted to evaluate the influence of technologies on economics—in such spheres, for example, art and design, advertising, and journalism, and specific groups of people, including, for instance, students and professionals.

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In 2022, Rutkowski and other designers expressed concerns that, when his name was used as a prompt in AI art generators, images resembling his unique style were being generated. The artists argued that their works were being used without permission to train AI models, which then produced new works mimicking their styles, effectively infringing on their intellectual property rights. Many such cases are still ongoing, and a definitive legal conclusion has yet to be reached. No party has been found legally at fault as there has been no proper framework or precedent set, and AI generation is a testament to human innovation.

This controversy highlights an ethical dilemma that has emerged with the rise of AI in creative fields: while AI-generated art represents a groundbreaking technological achievement, it simultaneously challenges traditional notions of authorship and intellectual property.

The debate surrounding AI-generated art has sparked questions beyond plagiarism and ownership, touching on the concept of originality itself. Traditional ideas of originality involve an artist's unique interpretation and creative process; however, AI-generated works blur these boundaries by producing images that mimic artistic styles based on patterns in vast datasets. This raises questions about the essence of creativity and whether AI, a machine-learning tool drawing on human-created content, can truly create something original.

As AI models are trained on large datasets of existing images, often without the consent of creators, artists are concerned that these systems exploit their work without fair recognition or compensation. This lack of regulation puts designers and artists in an uncertain position, where their creative labour may inadvertently compete against them as AI imitates their work in seconds.

In response to these challenges, artists are urging clearer guidelines to regulate AI in art and design. With no established legal precedents, AI's use in art remains legally ambiguous, leaving the industry to navigate both its potential and ethical issues. While AI-generated art is popular, there is still limited understanding of how designers—especially in non-Western contexts like India—view these tools and their effect on creativity and professional integrity.

Given the gap in understanding the global impacts of AI technology on designers, particularly in non-Western contexts like India, this research aims to examine the perceptions of Indian graphic design students and professionals toward AI-generated art, exploring how these views affect their definitions of originality and ethical considerations. The objectives of this study include understanding what designers consider original art in the context of AI, investigating how these perceptions influence their creative processes, examining how frequently and for what purposes they use AI image generators, and exploring the relationship between their definitions of originality and their use of AI. Insights from this research could guide design education, inform ethical guidelines for AI integration, and enrich industry discussions on the evolving definitions of originality and creativity in the digital age.

2. Literature Review

2.1. Introduction to AI in Graphic Design and Creative Fields

Generative models, especially GANs, have become powerful tools for creating visuals that connect with audiences, helping make creative work more efficient across industries such as advertising and marketing (Casteleiro-Pitrez, 2024). By automating repetitive tasks, AI tools give designers more time to explore other skills and adapt to new demands in a constantly changing field (Chacko, 2024). AI's ability to analyze patterns, themes, and techniques also deepens our understanding of creativity, which shows its potential as a tool not just for making art, but for understanding it (Then et al., 2023).

2.2. Defining Originality in the Context of AI-Generated Art

The rise of AI-generated art has raised new questions about the definition of 'original' or 'authentic' art. Traditionally, creativity has been defined as the ability to come up with new ideas that serve specific purposes, like problem-solving or communication (Rodriguez, 2023). But with AI now able to perform tasks that previously required human input, such as generating ideas and improving product quality, defining what makes art 'original' has become more challenging. Some people argue that AI-generated art takes away from the uniqueness of human-made work, while others think it can make original art more valuable by emphasizing its irreplaceable qualities (Çeken & Akgöz, 2023). Distinguishing AI-generated

art from human-made art is increasingly difficult as technology evolves. This challenge raises questions about what makes art genuinely creative (Lima et al., 2021; Ha et al., 2024).

2.3. Ethical and Legal Issues: Copyright, Authorship, and Data Usage

The use of AI in art also brings up significant ethical and legal issues, especially when it comes to copyright, authorship, and data usage (Janjetović et al., 2023). Many AI models are trained on large datasets that often include copyrighted or uncredited work, sometimes without permission from the original creators. Artists and designers argue that this kind of uncredited use undermines their creative rights and threatens their income (Goetze, 2024). To address these issues, some ethical frameworks suggest guidelines, like requiring consent before adding art to datasets, giving creators the option to remove their work from these databases, and prioritizing individual artist rights over corporate interests (Ghosh & Fossas, 2022). Some researchers argue that using web-hosted art without permission to train AI is morally questionable, and that using any form of creative media without the creator's consent—whether text, video, or audio—should also be viewed as unethical (Goetze, 2024). In many places, though, copyright ownership in AI-generated work tends to go to the producer of the work rather than the creator (Mihăilă, 2023). For Indian designers, who may have limited legal protections, these ethical and legal challenges highlight the importance of developing transparent AI practices that respect artists' creative rights (Kirley, 2023).

2.4. Impact of AI on Professional Practice and Career Expectations in Design

AI is changing what's expected of designers in their careers and the skills they need to succeed. Designers now face pressure to integrate AI into their work to stay competitive, as AI tools improve efficiency and enhance creative processes (Shi et al., 2023). Some designers report that using AI has led to increased productivity and profits, but those who resist AI can face challenges, like fewer job opportunities in a market that increasingly values AI skills (Shi et al., 2023). This situation can put designers in a difficult spot: they need to adopt generative AI to avoid becoming obsolete, or they risk falling behind in a fast-moving job market (Mustafa, 2023).

While AI has the potential to complement or even replace human creativity in some aspects of graphic design, overreliance could result in a generation lacking deep knowledge in their fields (Meron, 2022). Although AI is not yet capable of fully replacing humans, it may reach that point in the future (Evans, 2024). Understanding these perspectives is crucial for stakeholders to integrate AI into the art world in a way that complements, rather than displaces, human creativity (Wang, 2024). Ultimately, the enduring value of human qualities—originality, creativity, empathy, and the "human touch"—remains vital in all disciplines, including design (Tomić et al., 2023).

There's a growing emphasis on continuous skill development as AI spreads across different areas of design. Without a strong foundation in core design principles, there's a risk that relying too much on AI could lower the quality of design work (Karaata, 2018). This is especially important for young designers and students who are preparing to enter a field where both AI skills and traditional design expertise are highly valued. For Indian designers, this dual expectation calls for a balance between learning AI tools and maintaining high standards in creative quality (Gallardo et al., 2023; Longhurst, 2024).

2.5. Public Perceptions of AI in Art and Design

Public and cultural perceptions play a big role in shaping attitudes toward AI-generated art, and media representations are an important part of this (Dhawka et al., 2024). Studies show that media—whether it's news, movies, or science fiction—can have a significant impact on public opinion about AI, contributing to both support and skepticism toward AI's role in creative fields (Mitrani & Gu, 2024).

2.6. Identified Gaps and Contribution of this Study

While existing research has examined AI's impact on design, originality, and ethics, most studies focus on Western contexts, with limited attention given to culturally diverse environments like India. Additionally, there is little research on the differing perspectives of students and professionals regarding AI-generated art, originality, and ethical considerations. This study aims to address these gaps by exploring the views of Indian graphic designers—both students and professionals—on

AI's effects on originality, ethical issues, and career expectations in a context where tradition and digital innovation are often closely linked.

3. Methodology

3.1. Study Design

This study employed a quantitative, between-subjects design to compare the perceptions of AI tools in design between two groups: graphic design students and industry professionals. The participant groups consisted of 20 individuals in each, selected for varying levels of experience in design, providing diverse insights.

3.1.1. Participants

Participants included 20 design students from Indian institutes and 20 industry professionals, ranging from freelancers and studio founders to designers working in corporations.

3.1.2. Procedure

A structured survey was created, and the participants were chosen to provide insights into their differing perspectives across three categories:

- Creative Adaptability
- Originality Integrity Concern
- Technological Transition Anxiety

The survey results were scored using a 5-point Likert scale. Mean scores and standard deviations were calculated for each category to identify trends and variations between the two groups.

3.1.3. Variables

Independent variable: The group of participants (students vs. professionals)

Dependent variables: The scores on the questionnaires concerning the impact of AI on creativity, perceived threat, and ethical considerations.

3.2. Interviews

To gain an in-depth insight into the perceptions of graphic designers towards AI-generated art, semi-structured interviews were conducted with both graphic design students and working professionals.

3.2.1. Participants Selection

Participants included graphic design students and working professionals, chosen to represent a broad range of experience levels. Student participants were selected from relevant programs. Professionals were identified based on their industry experience in graphic design.

3.2.2. Procedure

Interviews were semi-structured, allowing flexibility for participants to express their opinions and allow for varied points of view. The interviews were conducted both in person and virtually, lasting from 20 minutes to an hour. Topics included definitions of originality, the role of AI in creativity, the frequency and purpose of AI tool usage, and ethical considerations.

3.3. Data Recording and Analysis

Interviews were audio-recorded with participants' consent and transcribed for thematic analysis. This helped identify key themes related to perceptions of AI-generated art and its impact on the design practices of graphic designers.

3.4. Ethical Considerations

Informed consent was obtained from all participants and responses were anonymized to maintain confidentiality.

4. Results

4.1. Study Insights

The study revealed notable disparities between design students and professionals in their perceptions and utilization of AI tools. On the **Creative Adaptability Index**, professionals scored an average of 4.0 (SD = 0.7), indicating their ability to embrace AI as a complementary tool that enhances their workflow and creativity. Conversely, students scored 3.5 (SD = 0.9), reflecting a more cautious approach to AI integration.

The **Originality Integrity Concern (OIC)** scores highlighted significant apprehensions among students about AI's impact on creativity and personal expression, with a mean score of 4.4 (SD = 0.8). This aligns with concerns noted by Rodriguez (2023) about AI disrupting traditional definitions of originality. Professionals, with a lower mean score of 3.7 (SD = 0.6), displayed a more pragmatic view, possibly influenced by industry familiarity with AI tools as augmentative rather than substitutional (Casteleiro-Pitrez, 2024).

For **Technological Transition Anxiety (TTA)**, students had a higher mean score of 4.2 (SD = 0.9), indicating fears of displacement due to automation, which resonates with Shi et al. (2023) on entry-level job vulnerability. Professionals' lower TTA score of 3.6 (SD = 0.7) reflected confidence in adapting to new tools, aligning with Karaata's (2018) emphasis on skill development. Several key patterns emerged (Figure 1);

Figure 1. Dual Bar Graph Comparing Professionals and Students on Creative Adaptability, Originality Integrity Concern, And Technological Transition Anxiety Indices

4.1.1. Creative Co-Driver Effect

Professionals embraced AI as a facilitator for mundane tasks and ideation, enhancing productivity and creativity. This reflects the findings of Chacko (2024), who emphasized AI's role in automating repetitive tasks while enabling higher-order thinking. Students limited their use of AI to specific functions, underutilizing its potential.

4.1.2. Concerns with Originality

Students expressed significant fears about AI undermining creativity, echoing Goetze (2024) on the perceived erosion of artistic authenticity. Professionals emphasized AI's role in supporting, not replacing, human creativity, consistent with Lima et al. (2021).

4.1.3. Technological Transition Awareness

Professionals demonstrated awareness of AI's short adoption cycles, aligning with Casteleiro-Pitrez (2024) on the importance of staying up to date. Students, however, showed reliance on outdated tools, highlighting a gap in exposure to emerging technologies.

4.1.4. Ethical Boundaries

Both groups agreed on the "Principle of Final Authorship," stressing human oversight in creative outputs. This reflects (Ghosh & Fossas 2022) on ethical frameworks for AI in design.

4.1.5. Career Pathways and Anxiety

Students worried about AI automating foundational roles, consistent with Mitrani and Gu (2024) on media-driven anxieties. Professionals viewed AI as democratizing design access; a sentiment echoed by Longhurst (2024).

4.2. Interview Insights

4.2.1. AI as a Workflow Enhancer

Professionals reported using AI primarily for time-consuming and repetitive tasks, allowing them to focus on strategic and conceptual work. One professional noted, "AI improves the building blocks, and the actual design is made from understanding how that time can be best utilized." Students, while acknowledging the convenience AI provides, were cautious about over-reliance, with one stating, "It assists me in setting the stage, but I take it from there."

4.2.2. The Nature of Originality

Students linked originality to personal creativity, with one remarking, "Art loses its authenticity when it does not come from me." Professionals adopted a broader perspective, integrating AI-generated components while ensuring final outputs retained a human touch. One professional emphasized, "True originality always requires adding the human layer."

4.2.3. Best Practice Boundaries and Ethical Positions

Both groups maintained that AI should not perform the final steps of creative work. Students stressed the need to sustain their creative voice, while professionals highlighted ethical concerns surrounding authorship. This aligns with the "Principle of Final Authorship," which prioritizes human input in final outputs.

4.2.4. Career Pathways

Students expressed anxiety about entry-level job opportunities being replaced by AI, describing this as a potential barrier to gaining foundational experience. Professionals, however, viewed AI as enabling broader access to design by handling basic tasks for clients with limited budgets, potentially creating demand for advanced design roles.

4.2.5. Continuous Learning as a Necessity

Professionals emphasized the importance of adapting to new AI tools to remain competitive, framing this as part of their "Sustained Competence Strategy." While recognizing the need to stay current, students prioritized mastering fundamental design skills before incorporating advanced AI capabilities.

5. Discussion

5.1. Interpreting Results

The results underscore the interplay between adaptability, concerns about originality, and technological awareness. Professionals' higher scores on adaptability reflect their familiarity with integrating AI into workflows, supported by sustained competence strategies (Bengtsson & Lindqvist, 2024). Students' lower adaptability and higher anxiety highlight a need for exposure to AI's practical applications in education (Gallardo et al., 2023).

5.1.1. Adaptability and Experimentation

Professionals' frequent experimentation with AI tools enables strategic integration, consistent with the "Creative Co-Driver Effect." In contrast, students' protective stance on originality limits experimentation, underscoring Çeken and Akgöz's (2023) call for balanced curricula that integrate traditional and AI skills.

5.1.2. Anxiety and Perceptions of Originality

Students' heightened concerns about originality reflect a media-influenced dystopian narrative, as noted by Brewer et al. (2024). Professionals' balanced view on AI's role as an assistant rather than a replacement. Addressing these divergent perceptions in education could mitigate fears and enhance acceptance.

5.1.3. Navigating Technological Transitions

The "Adoption Window Awareness" among professionals demonstrates strategic agility in leveraging AI, echoing Chacko's (2024) insights on maintaining relevance through continuous learning. Students' reliance on outdated tools highlights a gap in dynamic learning environments, necessitating curricular updates (Chacko, 2024).

5.2. Implications for Education and Practice

5.2.1. For Design Education

The curriculum should include AI modules that emphasize technical skills, ethical considerations, and hands-on experience with emerging tools, as suggested by Lee and Zhang (2023). AI has great potential, offering features that cater to the unique needs of diverse student populations, thus fostering inclusivity (Omran et al., 2024).

5.2.2. For Professional Development

Training programs should focus on continuous learning and strategic use of AI (Ekaterinushkina et al., 2024), balancing automation with human creativity (Longhurst, 2024).

5.2.3. Bridging Perception Gaps

Addressing media-driven anxieties and fostering a balanced understanding of AI's role can reshape student attitudes, aligning with Mitrani and Gu's (2024) findings on media influence.

6. Conclusion

This study highlights contrasting perspectives on AI adoption among students and professionals. While professionals use AI to enhance workflows and creativity, students remain cautious, hindered by originality concerns and displacement fears. The "Creative Co-Driver Effect" and "Adoption Window Awareness" among professionals demonstrate effective AI integration, while students' "Originality Integrity Concerns" and "Technology Transition Anxiety" underscore the need for targeted educational interventions.

Integrating AI training into design curricula and promoting its ethical use in professional practice can harness AI's potential while preserving human creativity. Future research should explore longitudinal shifts in perceptions, the role of media in shaping attitudes, and strategies for aligning educational outcomes with industry demands.

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